

Incorporating Pattern Recognition Skills into Mathematics Curriculum as a Basis for Effective Learning of Mathematics

Aasa, Moses Adebowale

Department of Mathematics, Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate
aasamoses@yahoo.com, +2348030767949

&

Adigun, Olatunde Thomas

Department of General Studies (Science Unit), Oyo State College of Education, Lanlate
thomasadigun@yahoo.com, +2348030709721

Abstract

One of the objectives of education is to improve the quality and relevance of educational experience of learners so that recognized and measurable learning outcomes can be obtained. That Mathematics, being fundamental to meaningful development, holds the key to social and economic fortunes of any society is no longer disputable. This study therefore explores the incorporation of pattern recognition skills into Mathematics curriculum for a growing need so as to transform the learning of the subject at various levels. Hence, the paper examined the importance of mathematics, curriculum and pattern recognition and rounded it off with some challenges and how to overcome the identified shortcomings. It therefore concluded that it is not only to understand the abstract nature of the subject but also to explore how pattern recognition can be of help and finally came up with the recommendations that relevant educated agencies should brace up and provide conducive learning environment in favour of incorporating pattern recognition into Mathematics curricular right from the basic level.

Keywords: Mathematical connection, Real-world Application, Cognitive bias, Pattern Recognition Skills

For Citation:

Aasa, M. A., & Adigun, O. T. (2025). Incorporating pattern recognition skills into mathematics curriculum as a basis for effective learning of mathematics. *Journal of Science Scholars*, 3(1), 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15680362>

Introduction

Mathematics is an essential school subject which has its relevance to man's daily activities. It is an essential component of every human's way of life that respond to its environmental needs. Based on this realization, every society ascribes some level of seriousness to the teaching and learning of Mathematics from elementary practices of counting, measuring and describing the shapes of objects. According to Abdullahi (2017), Mathematics knowledge spreads across all spheres of human enterprise and as such, there is no subject or field of study that does not make use of some form of Mathematics or the other. Adedayo (2017) summited that knowledge of Mathematics promotes the habit of accuracy, logical, systematic and orderly arrangements of facts in the individual learner. While Garba (2020) believe that mathematics encourages the habit of self-reliance and assist learners to think and solve their problems themselves. Davis (2021) described Mathematics as a means of equipping the child with special powerful tools.

Despite the importance of Mathematics to individual and indeed country's overall development, students still get low grades in Mathematics in both internal examinations and those conducted by external examination bodies like the West Africa Examinations Council (WAEC), National Examinations Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). Nwadiage (2010), Ayanwoye and Adesina (2011), Matawal (2013) and Kolawole and Ajetunmobi (2014), all attested to the fact that learners' achievement in Mathematics at primary and secondary levels have to continue to be poor. Some researchers attributed the low achievement in Mathematics to students' lack of interest, poor instructional strategies, poor learning strategies, incompetence in teaching certain mathematical concepts, among others (Obioma 2015, Obinweluozo, 2015). To Adeniyi (2009), the cause of the widespread low-level performance of students in mathematics could be largely ascribed to mechanical and uninteresting teaching methods adopted which are devoid of understanding of the real meaning of mathematical concepts. Kurumeh and Iji (2009) asserted that if students are given the chance to experience Mathematics' beauty during Mathematics lesson, their phobia and sense of difficulty in mathematics will vanish.

The major difficult task to learning Mathematics in our schools nowadays is how to learn Mathematics and how to apply or use the already learnt concepts in Mathematics in their day-to-day activities. Several studies have repeated the effects of different forms of instructional strategies on students' achievement. Researchers like Chianson, Kurumeh and Obida (2011), Van (2014) and Olaitan and Ogundoyin (2015) reported that cooperate learning strategies enhance students achievement in Mathematics. They all agreed that effective learning approaches increase the quality of learning, that students learn best by doing and experiencing. The teaching approaches/methods adopted by teachers can make the learners develop low motivation or high interest towards Mathematics learning tasks. However, the present study intends to find out how effective it will be, if pattern recognition is incorporated into Mathematics curriculum.

Curriculum means many things to many experts Aminu (2005) defined curriculum as a prescribed course of study students must fulfill in order to pass a certain level of education. Offoma (2005) saw it as a planned learning experience offered to a student which can be divided into three components/ programs: activities, studies and guidance. Alade (2011) saw curriculum as the

medium which educational institutions seek to translate societal values into concrete reality. To Abdu (2014), curriculum is a set of planned and guided learning experience or the learners' continuous and willful growth. In addition to this, Lawal (2020) opined that curriculum is a document which contains the needs of society stated in goals and objectives with arranged content and learning experience that are expected to be transferred to the learners for better transformation of the learners and the society.

Mathematics curriculum, on the other hand, is the plan for the experiences that learners encounter, as well as the actual experiences they do encounter, that are designed to help them reach specified Mathematics objectives (<https://www.igi-global.com>). In addition to this, Obande and Dogo (2018) described Mathematics curriculum as the total programme of instructions offered in institutions which has to do with repositioning and learning experiences for meeting education aims, objectives and goals with respect to the need of the society. According to Obande and Dogo (2018), the implication of Mathematics curriculum is that it must be:

1. integrated with current challenges of the society;
2. flexible to change as the society strives to change for better development;
3. responsive to the norms and values of the society that gives learners' sense of belonging;
4. provides adequate study and use of proper language for communication purpose;
5. develop critical thinking, creativity and innovation in students, which is needed for societal developments;
6. such that its learning resources are adequately available for efficient and effective teaching and learning;
7. it is socially relevant by being localized with experiences drawn locally within the immediate environment and;
8. gives opportunity for improvisation of instructional materials.

There are strategies that some Mathematics educators and researchers have come up with that could enhance the teaching and learning of Mathematics. This study focus on incorporating pattern recognition into Mathematics curriculum. Teaching and learning of some topics in Mathematics is based on pattern and structure. Warren (2005) opined that the power of Mathematics lies in relations and transformations which give rise to patterns and generalizations which is the basis of structural knowledge that serves as goal of Mathematics learning. Pattern is an arrangement of lines or shapes, especially a design in which the same shape is repeated at regular intervals over a shape (Collins English Dictionary. <https://www.collindictionary.com>) and, Cambridge Dictionary defines a pattern as any regularly repeated arrangement, especially a design made from repeated lines, shapes or colour on a surface (<https://dictionary.canbrigde.org>). In Mathematics, a pattern is defined as a sequence of repeating objects, shapes or numbers that can be finite or infinite (<https://splashlearn.com>). In other words, a pattern consists of an arrangement of numbers, shapes, colours, and pictures etc. that are repeated in a certain order. Pattern recognition therefore is the scientific discipline that is concerned with the description and classification of objects. Yasin and Nusantara (2023) asserted that pattern recognition is a helpful

tool for processing and understanding information that are essential part of solving problems or creating intentional outcomes. In Mathematics, formulae and algorithms abound in everything from basic times table to calculus and other topics. For instance, students recognize the specific formulae used to calculate slopes and intercepts.

Characteristics of Pattern Recognition

The characteristics of pattern recognition for solving Mathematics problems according to Yasin and Nusantara (2023) are identified as follows:

1. **Foundational understanding:** This is the process whereby students understand the problem by looking for information on the problem context. It assists students in grasping relations in Mathematics as well as pattern in Mathematics. For instance, an ability to identify sequences and geometric progressions is elementary to comprehending algebraically and mathematically.
2. **Problem-solving skills:** It enables the students to extract the problems components and look for a relationship or otherwise from the extraction. This is a useful tool because it gives units and short cuts whilst solving problem. When students realize repetition, they create ways on how they are going to solve that particular problem so as not to work on it for a long time. Also, pattern recognition helps the students to match questions with a similar description of questions stored in the students' memory or past information.
3. **Predictive power:** Pattern recognition facilitates students' ability to make prediction. That is, it helps students to find from the forecast results based on the problem at hand. For instance, to find the n th term in a sequence directly, one has to compute the previous terms, while if one understands the pattern, one can figure out the next term in the sequence directly.
4. **Mathematical connections:** Pattern recognition enables students in grasping relationships between various topic areas in Mathematics. That is to say the students should be able to exploit all possible relationship from the extraction results to find regularity. For example, if teachers take the pain of explaining geometry in details, it gives the students the ability to recognize the relationship between different component of geometric shapes as well as algebraic formulae

Strategies for Incorporating Patterns Skills in Mathematics

1. **Interactive and Hands-on Activities:** This is a teaching method that engages students in Mathematics uses in a more hands-on-way. According to Ekwueme, Ekon and Ezenwa-Nebife (2015), hand-on strategy means giving the students the opportunity to manipulate the objects they are learning or studying. They concluded that it is a process of learning mathematics and science where students become active participants in the classroom. Hands-on activities approach involves the child in a total learning experience which enhances the child's ability to think critically. Using manipulative objects such as puzzles and game like Sudoku, Crossword among others can help to sharpen students' attention,

meaning, logic, creativity and train their brain to recognize and apply patterns in different context.

According to Ekwueme et al (2015), the hands-on approach has the following merits. It helps to increase students' academic achievement and understanding of concepts by manipulating objects which may look abstract, more concrete and clearer. Students are able to engage in real life illustrations and observe the changes in different shapes or variables under study. Also, it helps the learner to see, touch and manipulate shapes while learning Mathematics, and this makes the learning more of seeing and doing than hearing.

2. **Early Introduction and Gradual Complexity:** Introducing pattern recognition in early Mathematics education encourages learners to share ideas and try out different methods of problem-solving. At this stage, learners quickly gain confidence, make use of mathematical vocabulary freely, not minding making mistakes and get used to explaining what they are doing. The utmost goal or objective for teachers is to accelerate learners into the next level as quickly as possible through the following ways:

- i. coherence, that is, the ability to break lessons into small and connected steps;
- ii representation and structure which helps to reveal the mathematical structure to the learners;
- iii. mathematical thinking and ideas are worked on, reasoned with and discussed with others;
- iv. fluency, at this stage, learners are able to recall quickly and efficiently the facts and procedure follow in solving a problem.

3. **Integration across Mathematical Curriculum:** Integrated curriculum, according to Adamu (2003), is an educational approach that prepares students for lifelong learning. In other words, curriculum integration is a way to increase students' understanding by teaching across various topics, teaching according to their natural connections rather than in isolation from one another. This approach develops the students' ability to transfer their learning to other settings. In arithmetic operations, there exists relationship that can help in mastering the multiplication tables and factors. For example "4, 9, 14, 24, 29, 34, 39, -, - , -" is a pattern that is created by using the five times table and taking away one each term. In algebra, individual teachers can look for different pattern in equations to make the solving of the equations easier. Also, in Geometry, an experienced Mathematics teacher often can see certain patterns in geometric shapes and their everyday applications which may help the students in proofing theorems.

Integrating across learning of Mathematics or others subjects has been found to be useful. According to Moss, Godinho and Chao (2019), it:

- i. leads to deeper learning by shifting from surface learning and context coverage to in-depth understanding,
- ii. increases students' engagement and motivation,
- iii. leads to enhanced academic performance of students,
- iv. provides an effective way to teach 21st century thinking and skills,

v. leads to increase subject self-confidence and self-awareness, so students form positive relations and recognize their place in their community.

4. Real-world Application of Mathematics: Mathematics is often considered a difficult subject by students. The reason behind this is that topics such as algebra and calculus often seem absent and disconnected from our daily lives, leaving many students questioning the practicality of studying them. Connecting Mathematics with real-life applications can make the subject matter less abstract and more engaging. This approach helps students understand its relevance and can lead to deeper comprehension, enabling them to apply their mathematical knowledge and skills for future treatments. For instance, the Pythagorean theorem has many practical real applications and is used regularly in architectural design. The evidence is in bridges, ramps, houses and building which utilize right triangles and the Pythagorean theorem to shape sloped roofs with the 90° angle located at the top. In addition to this, exponential functions (often refers to as multiple vision in Biology) are often used in biological studies to measure bacterial growth and decay. For example, if a bacterial cell splits itself into two, then each of those two cells split into two, etc you will quickly have bacterial cells in numbers of 1,2, 4, -, -, -

5. Using technology and digital tools: Integrating technology into the mathematics classroom is crucial because nowadays students are inseparable from it. It can help students to visualize abstract mathematical concepts, make connections between mathematical ideas and actively engage with the material (Rashidov, 2020). Since technology is embedded in their lives, using digital tools will enable teacher to attract the student's attention, adapt class to student's needs, and let them make sense of the mathematical content they have learnt. Since no two students are the same, integrating technology in the mathematics classroom will aid teachers in creating and tailored learning experiences and supporting everybody.

Benefits of Pattern Recognition Skill Usage

Developing pattern recognition skills in solving Mathematics in students offers several benefits. These include:

1. It enhances students' logical reasoning and critical thinking abilities. By practicing in the identification of patterns, teacher is able to draw improvements in aspects of the brain like the memory, mental focus and logical thinking which improves problem-solving skills. These skills are not limited to Mathematics only but also can be applied throughout other subjects taught in the school and real-life problems.
2. It prepares students for advance studies. By engaging students in pattern recognition activities, teacher can assist students with a solid foundation for a future academic success and a lifelong passion for learning. A perfect understanding of patterns is useful at elementary stages for topics like linear algebra, calculus and discrete Mathematics among others which students may likely faced later in life.
3. It also improves mathematical proficiency. Pattern recognition develops the ability to recognize and predict patterns in different contexts. Students who demonstrate a good

ability in pattern recognition can do well in Mathematics, they will be able to solve problems with effectiveness and confidence, which will result in better grades on academic related tasks.

4. Finally, it increases students' engagement and motivation. Pattern recognition can be enjoyable and challenging if properly handle by experts in the field, which tends to enhance the student's interest in STEAM subjects/ As a result, when students begin to derive pleasure from discovering certain pattern, they stand to develop a positive attitude and then serve as a motivation towards Mathematics.

Challenges of using Pattern Recognition Skills in Mathematics classes

As powerful and useful as pattern recognition is, it is also challenging. The following shows how our totality of intensions and abilities can be compromised when we rely solely on the dexterity of pattern recognition:

1. **Shallow understanding:** In Mathematics class, students often focus on little depth properties of the initial situations they encounter in terms of examples or/and problems without understanding or recognizing the general principle involved. So when a new situation arises, they either lack the general concept to have learnt or lack the skill of identifying key ideas in the problem at hand. Many students get 'lost' in Mathematics by the time they get into algebra because they haven't learned about those numerical relationships which they could have understood from elementary stages and because they were not nurtured to even seek relationships among numbers, they only learned numbers and numerical manipulations as facts.
2. **Cognitive bias:** This happens when a student tends to seek, interpret, or favour information that confirms his/her existing beliefs. This makes them to ignore or dismiss evidence that contradicts their assumptions or solutions only to focus on the aspects of the problem that support the approach they are using. For example, when solving a system of equations in which students have preempted idea of what the answer would be, the students may overlook mistakes in their calculations or fail to check for accuracy.
3. Other challenges are: limited contextual understanding, insufficient practice on the part of the students, and lack of connection of pattern recognition to mathematical concepts by the mathematics teachers, shortage of qualify Mathematics teachers among others.

To overcome these difficulties:

1. Students need to be taught or introduced to all possible number relationships in a meaningful way.
2. Teachers should encourage students to ask question(s) and verify their pattern identification.
3. Mathematics teachers should try as much as possible to connect pattern recognition to real-world applications and more complex situations.
4. Mathematics teachers are encouraged to be friendly in the class by encouraging students to practice and reinforce them when necessary.

Conclusion

Mathematics has immense potential to empower individuals to become informed, responsible and innovative citizens who can contribute to a more sustainable future development of any society. Therefore, it is important, not only to understand abstract nature of mathematical concepts but also to explore how pattern recognition can be of help and be integrated into Mathematics curriculum for the betterment of our great nation Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made for the effective learning of Mathematics if pattern recognition were incorporated into the mathematics curriculum of the country:

1. Governments should employ only qualified Mathematics teachers to teach Mathematics in our secondary schools and give appropriate seminars /trainings /workshops from time to time on pattern recognition efficacy.
2. Mathematics educators should be versed in the area of pattern recognition to enable them use the appropriate method in imparting Mathematics information across to the learners; and
3. Relevant agencies should provide enabling learning environment in favour of incorporating pattern recognition into mathematics programmes /curricular right from elementary stage.

References

- Abdu, B. M. (2014). Assessment of the implementation of math curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in Kano State, Unpublished M.ED Thesis submitted to faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Abdullahi, U. (2017). Impact of Group Based Mastery Learning Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students Trigonometric performance & Retention in Kastina state, Nigeria. In the proceedings of Annual National Conference of Mathematical Association of Nigeria, 511-519.
- Adedayo, O. (2017). Mathematics Phobia Diagnosis and Prescription. National Mathematical Centre 1st Annual Lecture, Abuja.
- Adeniyi, C.O. (2009). Effects of personalized system of instruction on senior school students' performance in mathematics in Kwara south, Nigeria unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Alade, I.A. (2011). Trends and issues on curriculum review in Nigeria and the need for paradigm shift in Educational practice. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 2(5), 325-333.
- Aminu, S. (2005). A survey of problems of mathematics teaching in Primary and Junior Secondary Schools in Bauchi State, unpublished M.Ed Thesis. Department of Education, University of Abuja.
- Ayanwoye, O.K and Adesina, A.E.(2011). Effect of medium of Instruction on the achievement of Secondary School Students in mathematics. *Journal of Arts and Social Sciences update*, 4 (2), 146-151.
- Cambridge Dictionary. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>

- Chianson, M. M., Kurumeh, M. S. & Obida (2011). Effect of Co-operative learning strategy on students' retention in circle Geometry in Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria. *American Journal of science and Industrial Research*, 2 (1), 33-36.
- Collins English Dictionary. <https://www.collindictionary.com>
- Davis, B. (2021). Why Mathematics is the most important subject? Available @ <https://www.mrorga>.
- Ekwueme, C. O., Ekon, E. E Ezenwa-Nebife (2015). The impact of Hands-On-Approach on students' academic performance in basic science and mathematics. *Higher Education Studies*, 5 (6), 47-51.
- Garba, A. (2020). Effect of teaching methods on the performance of mathematics students in public Secondary Schools in Markurdi Metropolis, Benue state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Mathematical Sciences & Applications*, 10 (1), 2-17.
- Kolawole, E. B & Ajetunmobi, O. (2014). Kolawole's problem solving (KPS) method as a panacea for mathematical problems and antidote to mass failure in Mathematics examinations. *Abacus, Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 39 (1), 159-176.
- Kurumeh, M.S & Iji, C.O. (2009). Improving students' Achievement in solving Algebraic word problems using Aesthetics value approach. *Abacus: The Journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 34 (1), 37-45.
- Lawal, S. (2020). Mathematics Curriculum Implementation in Nigeria Junior Secondary Schools. *African Scholars Journal of contemporary Education Researcher*, 18 (8), 225-234.
- Matawel, D. B. (2013). Analysis of the relationship between student's achievement in mathematics in SSCE and remedial sciences program, University of Jos-Nigeria. *Comprehensive Journal of Educational Research*, 1 (3), 42-46.
- Moss, J, Godinho, S.C & Chao, E.(2019). Enacting the Australian Curriculum: Primary and Secondary Teachers' Approach to Integrating the curriculum. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*. 44 (3), 24-41.
- Nwadiage, A. (2010), WAEC records 75% failure in English language and mathematics. The nation newspaper of August 28, 1-2.
- Obande, O. E and Dogo, J. D. (2018). Mathematics Teachers' Education curriculum repositioning through teaching of fractions with concrete representational strategy in Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. 55th Annual Proceedings Conference of Mathematical Association of Nigeria, 433-441.
- Obinweluozo, E. P. (2015). Effect of self-instruction strategy on pupil's achievement and interest in Mathematics Published thesis virtual Library University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Obioma, U.A. (2015). Rebranding the strategies for Teaching Mathematics. The case of scaffolding. Proceeding of Annual National Conference of Mathematical Association of Nigeria.
- Offoma, G.C. (2005). Curriculum for wealth creation. Paper presented at the world Council for Curriculum and Instruction, held at the Federal College of Education, Kano, Nigeria.

- Olaitan, O. A. & Ogundoyin, I. K. (2015). Virtualization: A sustainable Resource Management Strategy in computing practices, IOSR. *Journal of Computer Engineering*. 17 (2), 67-70
- Rashidov, A. (2020). Use of Differentiation Technology in Teaching Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science*, 8 (7), 163.167.
- Van, D. T. (2014).The Effects of Cooperative Learning on the Academic Achievement and Knowledge Retention. *Journal of Higher Education*. 3 (2), 131-140.
- Warren, E. (2005). Young Children’s Ability to generalize the pattern rule for growing patterns. In chick, H & Vincent, J (Eds). Proceedings of the 29th conference of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education, 4; 305-312.
- Yasin, M. & Nusantara, T. (2023). Characteristics of pattern recognition to solve Mathematics Problems in computational thinking, Available @ <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0112171>